

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

Housing Satisfaction among Students in Tertiary Institutions in Calabar, Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The paper focused on examining the satisfaction of students with hostel accommodation in tertiary institutions in Calabar, Cross River State Nigeria. The study sought specifically to identify the level at which students were satisfied with hostel accommodation using fifteen (15) variables. In order to obtain data, three (3) tertiary institutions within the study area were purposively sampled. A total of 150 copies of questionnaire were distributed to residents in the school hostels. Specifically, 50 copies of questionnaire were distributed in each residential hostel in schools that were sample out. Analysis were done using both descriptive statistics such as frequencies and simple percentages as well as relative satisfaction index (RSI) to determine the level of satisfaction of students in the hostels. A five point Likert scale was adopted in explaining the level of satisfaction of students with the hostels. The findings revealed that the students were fairly satisfied with the quality, condition and general standards of the hostels in the study area. This is due to the fact that certain facilities that need to be on ground to boost satisfaction level of students were not adequately provided. For instance, it was noted that students do not have maximum access to ICT facilities in hostels. It was also revealed that privacy in hostels had the weakest contribution to student satisfaction in the hostels. In order to boost satisfaction of residents with hostel accommodation, it was suggested that hostels be maintained regularly to avoid deterioration of facilities. It was also recommended that more residential units be developed to accommodate students in the study area. Equally, the students' priority should be given concern in the housing development process.

Keywords: Environmental quality Hostel accommodation, housing quality, housing environment, level of satisfaction.

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1. Introduction

Housing is a fundamental need for human beings. It is regarded as a primary human need. Other needs of humans are food and clothing (Akpu and Sarah, 2015). Among the above basic needs of man, housing is ranked second only to food in the daily needs of humans (Ojikpong, Agbor and Emri, 2016). Generally, housing endows it owner with a social identity, thus integrating him with his immediate social milieu. Therefore, owning a house provides significant security and status in the society. Hence, housing has a profound influence on man's health, education, social behaviour, employment, productivity, awareness on development opportunities, safety, crime and general wellbeing. This justifies the fact that housing is more than mere shelter as it encompasses all the social services and utilities that go to make a community or neighbourhood a

livable environment (Ojikpong *et al.*, 2016). With housing, spaces for work, sleep, recreation as well as other social requirements are provided. Furthermore, housing units are required for various uses. For instance, in commercial uses, housing units are required for storage of goods as well as for shops and warehouses while in institutional uses, housing units are demanded to serve as administrative complexes and housing units are in high demand for residential purposes. The importance of housing has made access to housing units to remain a fundamental human right (UN Habitat, 2006). In educational institutions specifically, housing units are needed for classrooms, as well as to accommodate teaching and learning equipment/facilities, provide spaces for administration and accommodate staff and students. Against this backdrop, the need for housing units in the